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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Somatic embryogenesis in rice *Oryza sativa*, cultivar IR40

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Somatic embryogenesis is a preferred method of plant propagation *in vitro*. It allows rapid production of a large number of true-to-type plants. Plants derived through embryogenesis are unicellular in origin, and are likely to be more suitable for genetic, breeding, and mutation research.

We studied the efficiency of *O. sativa* regeneration through this pathway. Dehulled mature seeds and young panicles of rice variety IR40 were sterilized and used as explants. The materials were inoculated on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with 2 mg 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)/liter, 0.2 mg benzyl adenine (BAP)/liter, 3% sucrose, and 0.8% Difco Bacto agar (MS₃) at pH 5.8-5.9. MS₃ has been found optimum for callus induction in young rice panicles. The cultures were incubated in darkness at 26-27 °C. Induced calli were subcultured every 4 wk (1 passage).

From passages 5 to 9, embryogenic calli were transferred to a regeneration with 4 mg BAP/liter, 0.5 mg/indoleacetic acid (IAA)/liter, 0.5 mg

naphthalene acetic acid (NAA)/liter, 500 mg casein hydrolysate/liter, 3% sucrose, 0.8% Difco Bacto agar, pH 5.8-5.9 (MS₁₈₋₁). The cultures were incubated in continuous light, 3,000 lx intensity, at 26-27 °C.

Data on regenerated plants were gathered after 4 wk in MS₁₈₋₁ medium.

Regeneration efficiency decreased with the number of passages (see table). The decrease was more pronounced in seed-derived callus. Plants from inflorescence-derived cultures could still be regenerated after passage 9. Seed-derived callus regenerated only through passage 8. The explants did not differ in average plant production.

The longitudinal section shows that germinated embryoids were bipolar with scutellum, coleoptile, and coleorhiza,

indicating that plant regeneration was through embryogenesis (see figure). □

Longitudinal section of an embryoid showing synchronous development of coleoptile (CL) and coleorhiza (CR). SC = scutellum. IRRI, 1987.

Plant regeneration at different durations in culture of calli derived from young inflorescences and seeds of IR40. IRRI, 1987.

Passage	Young inflorescence-derived callus			Seed-derived callus			
	Calli plated (no.)	Calli responding		Calli plated (no.)	Calli responding		Av green plant production ^b (no.)
		no.	% ^a		no.	% ^a	
5	44	7	15.9	4.1	25	4	3.0
6	0	0	0	0	24	11	5.1
7	25	3	12.0	3.0	20	3	4.3
8	25	6	24.0	5.0	15	1	4.0
9	20	3	15.0	4.0	20	0	0

^a $\frac{\text{Total no. of calli responding}}{\text{Total no. of calli plated for regeneration}} \times 100$

^b Plants produced/calli-producing plant.